

EFIKASI DIRI MAHASISWA AKUNTANSI PADA MASA PANDEMI COVID-19

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk menguji pengaruh efikasi diri terhadap prestasi akademik mahasiswa Program Studi Akuntansi Universitas Bung Hatta, Padang pada masa pandemi COVID-19. Penelitian merupakan penelitian korelasional dan pengumpulan data dilakukan dengan menggunakan kuesioner. Populasi penelitian adalah mahasiswa Akuntansi yang aktif di Universitas Bung Hatta angkatan 2018-2020 berjumlah 303 orang. Sampel penelitian berjumlah 76 orang yang dipilih menggunakan *proportionate stratified random sampling technique*. Analisis data yang digunakan adalah regresi linier sederhana. Hasil analisis menunjukkan bahwa mahasiswa dapat mengefikasi diri pada masa pandemi COVID-19. Simpulan penelitian adalah efikasi diri berpengaruh positif terhadap prestasi akademik mahasiswa Akuntansi Universitas Bung Hatta.

Kata Kunci: efikasi diri; prestasi akademik; pandemi COVID-19.

Abstract

The purpose of the research was to examine the effect of self-efficacy on academic performance of students of the Accounting Program at Universitas Bung Hatta, Padang during the COVID-19 pandemic. This research was a correlational research and data collection was done by using a questionnaire. The population in the research was accounting students who were active at Universitas Bung Hatta in 2018-2020 totaling 303 people. The research sample was 76 people who were selected using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Analysis of the data used simple linear regression. The results of the analysis showed that students can be self-efficacy during the COVID-19 pandemic. The conclusion of the research was that self-efficacy has a positive effect on the academic performance of accounting students at Universitas Bung Hatta.

Keywords: *self-efficacy; academic performance; COVID-19 pandemic.*